

APPROACH FOR DRY TEXTILE COMPOSITE FORMING SIMULATION

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1 Introduction

Due to its high strength to weight ratio, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is widely used in the aerospace industry to reduce the weight of an aircraft. In the automotive industry CFRP had been used only in high-end vehicles. Automakers are gradually using more CFRP in mass production cars [1] because the development of resin transfer molding (RTM) [2] has reduced its cycle time to less than 10 minutes. Numerical simulation is essential to the vehicle design process, so numerical simulation of CFRP is strongly desired today.

Fabrics are usually used as a reinforcement in RTM. Dry fabric is formed at first. Then the resin is injected within this preformed dry fabric [3] and cured to create the final composite part. It is well known that the performance of the final composite part strongly depends on changes in fiber orientation during the process. Moreover wrinkling is major defect in preforming process. Preforming process simulation is very important to predict the change in dry fabric direction and forming defects like wrinkling.

The kinematic models [4-5] are mostly applied in industry. The kinematic models are geometrical mapping algorithms. In this approach, the material properties such as non-linear shear response and loading applications by blank-holder cannot be considered. So as a more accurate approach finite element method (FEM) has been studied by many researchers. Sharma et al. [6] and Skordos et al. [7] proposed a discrete model that combines truss elements within a unit cell to represent uncoupled tension and shear deformation modes. Boisse et al. [8] developed a anisotropic hyperelastic material model that independently calculates in the tension of warp and weft direction and in-plane shear for

simulating the strong anisotropic behavior of dry fabric.

The objective of this paper is to present an approach for dry fabric forming simulation by FEM. Starting point of our approach is meso-scale simulations to understand each of the dry fabric properties under in-plane deformations (tension, compression and shear) and out-plane deformation (bending). Then we propose a macroscopic FEM model that can describe not only the nonlinear and orthogonal in-plane properties but also the orthogonal out-plane bending property of the dry fabric. Finally, the hemispherical forming simulations are performed using both meso-scale and proposed macro-scale models. The behavior of the change in fiber orientation and wrinkling is verified by comparison with the meso-scale model.

2 Mesoscopic approach

Because the macroscopic behavior of dry fabric is determined by the deformation and the interaction of yarns at mesoscopic scale, meso-scale model that can describe in detail the fabric structure is proposed [9-11]. These models can calculate directly the mesoscopic phenomenon to predict the macroscopic material properties of dry fabric.

2.1 Modeling meso-scale dry textile

Fig.1. Plain weaves textile structure of meso-scale model.

Figure 1 shows the meso-scale model of the plain weaves textile. The geometrical data of the meso-

scale model is generated by WiseTex software [12] and FE modeling is implemented by MeshTex [13].

2.2 Mechanical behavior of dry textile

Figure 2 shows the meso-scale simulation models used in order to obtain the deformation mechanisms and the material properties under (a) uniaxial tension, (b) biaxial tension, (c) picture frame shear, (d) bias-extension shear, (e) in-plane compression and (f) out-plane bending. The elastic-orthotropic material is applied to the yarns and interaction of weft and warp is considered (friction coefficient $\mu = 0.3$) by commercial finite element code LS-DYNA [14].

Fig.2. Meso-scale simulations; (a) uniaxial tension, (b) biaxial tension, (c) picture frame, (d) bias-extension, (e) compression, (f) out-plane bending.

Figure 3 shows the mechanical properties under uniaxial and biaxial tensile deformations extracted from mesoscopic simulations. We can see that the undulation of yarns within the fabric is removed in uniaxial tension. That affects the low initial stiffness zone as long as yarns are being straightened. There is no low initial stiffness zone in the stress-strain curve of biaxial deformation because the biaxial load leads to elastic elongation of the yarn itself.

Fig.3. Responses to uniaxial and biaxial tension.

Next in relation to shear behavior, two tests methods are popularly used; picture frame and bias-extension [15]. We performed both simulations to obtain the behavior under shear deformation.

In the picture fame test, the fabric is clamped in the frame, which is mounted in a tensile machine (Figure 2 (c)). Shear angle γ and shear force F_{sh} are directly calculated as follows:

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \arccos\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} + \frac{d}{2L}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$F_{sh} = \frac{F_{norm}}{2\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} + \frac{d}{2L}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where d , L and F_{norm} are the loading displacement, the length of the specimen and the load on picture frame, respectively.

An alternative to the picture frame test is bias-extension test. This test is a tensile test performed on a rectangular specimen where the warp and weft yarns are oriented initially $\pm 45^\circ$ to the direction of applied tensile load (Figure.3 (d)). The bias-extension is easy to perform, but introduces an inhomogeneous deformation field. Under kinematic assumption (no deformation of yarns and no sliding between yarns), shear angle γ and shear force F_{sh} are calculated as follows [16]:

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \arccos\left(\frac{D+d}{\sqrt{2}D}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$F_{sh}(\gamma) = \frac{F_c}{\cos \gamma} \left(\cos\left(\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) \right) - F_{sh}\left(\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) \quad (4)$$

where d, D and F_c are the loading displacement, the length of pure shear zone (Figure 2 (d)) and the load cell force, respectively.

Shear characteristic obtained by both picture frame and bias-extension are strongly nonlinear as shown in Figure 4. The resistance against a changing shear angle is very low until reaching a shear locking angle and is controlled by weft and warp friction. Above shear locking angle, the shear modulus significantly increases due to internal yarn contact and distorted yarns. The shear stiffness by bias-extension is lower than that by picture frame. Boisse et al. [16] reported the reason for the difference is due to boundary conditions. The bias-extension test leads to a purer shear state without tension than the picture frame test, because the yarns are free at the end.

Fig.4. Response to shear loading.

Fig.5. Response to compression loading.

The compressive stiffness is very low in comparison to tensile stiffness because of mesoscopic

phenomenon such as the buckling of yarns as shown in Figure 5.

The resistance against bending is also very low, resulting from the yarn characteristics and textile construction. And the bending stiffness depends on the direction as shown in Figure 6.

Fig.6. Responses to pure bending in 0deg. and 45deg.

3 Macroscopic approach

In this section, we propose the macro-scale model that can simulate in-plane anisotropic behavior and out-plane bending stiffness similar to those that are obtained in meso-scale simulation.

Figure 7 shows the composition of the proposed macro-scale model.

Fig.7. Macro-scale model considering in-plane and out-plane properties.

3.1 Constitutive macro-scale model

In order to describe the in-plane anisotropic and nonlinear material behavior, hyperelastic material model that have an uncoupled stress update meaning that the stress is calculated independently in warp direction, weft direction and shear is proposed with membrane element.

Shell elements are duplicated on the membrane element to couple bending stiffness to it. The offset of the shell reference surface is applied so that in-plane properties will not be affected as explained later. In this model, it is assumed that the in-plane behavior and out-plane behavior are uncoupled. Furthermore, effects of off-axis bending stiffness

(Figure 6) can be calculated by giving an orthotropic material formulation to the duplicated shell element. We can give a small Young's modulus to the duplicated shell elements, enough not to affect the in-plane properties, but get effective bending stiffness.

3.2 Behavior of macro-scale model

We conduct some simulations shown in Figure 2. The load versus displacement curves from the macroscopic simulations are validated to those from the mesoscopic simulations as shown in Figure 8. We can see the proposed macro-scale model can reproduce the load versus displacement curves of the meso-scale model.

Stress versus strain curves for in-plane properties (tension, shear and compression) extracted from meso-scale simulations are introduced into the macro-scale model. Moreover, bending stiffness is given by the shell element, following equation (7). As it was mentioned earlier, bias-extension cannot introduce the homogeneous deformation field, so we cannot get the exact shear property directly from equations (3) and (4). Figure 8(b) shows the result after fitting the input shear stress versus shear strain curve property by the reverse engineering process.

Fig.8. Comparison; (a) uniaxial tension, (b) bias-extension shear, (c) compression, (d) bending.

4 Hemispherical preforming simulations

Hemispherical forming simulations are performed using both the meso-scale and macro-scale models. The size of the blank sheet of dry fabric is 156×156mm. The radius of the hemispherical part of the punch is 50 mm, and the travelling distance of the movable punch is 50 mm. Figure 9 shows the preforming simulation model.

Fig.9. FE preforming simulation on hemisphere.

4.1 Verification of change in fiber orientation

Figure 10 shows the deformation behavior of the meso-scale model and macro-scale model. Deformations at 20 mm, 30 mm, 40 mm and 50 mm punch stroke of the meso-scale model are shown in Figure 10(a). Green-Lagrange shear strain distributions of the macro-scale model at each punch stroke are depicted in Figure 10(b). Figure 10(c) illustrates the deformed square grid, comparing the meso-model and macro-model. Results for the fiber orientation of the macro-scale model follows the results of the meso-scale model very closely, with high shear deformation at four locations aligned to the bias direction.

Fig.10. Comparison of deformation and change in fiber orientation between meso-scale model and macro-scale model.

4.2 Verification of wrinkling

There is no remarkable wrinkle in both the meso-scale model and macro-scale model using a blank-holder. It is usually used to reduce wrinkling. Then, we conduct the preforming simulations without a blank-holder in order to verify the influence of the compression property and out-plane bending stiffness upon the wrinkling.

Figure 12 shows the deformed shape at 20 mm punch stroke. Figure 12 (a) is the meso-scale model. The wrinkling doesn't occur at this punch stroke. The deformed shape in the macro-scale model considering in-plane tension and in-plane shear properties is shown in Figure 12(b). In this model, the compressive stiffness is the same as the tensile stiffness. Many small wrinkles have occurred. Figure 12(c) shows the result when all in-plane

properties (tensile, shear and compressive) are considered. There are still too many wrinkles. Finally, Figure 12(d) shows the resultant deformation by the proposed model, considering not only the nonlinear and orthogonal in-plane properties but also orthogonal out-plane bending property. In this model, like the meso-scale model, the wrinkling is not observed at this punch stroke.

Figure 13 shows the deformed shapes at the 30 mm punch stroke. Many small wrinkles are observed in Figure 13(b) and (c). Figure 13(d) shows the deformed shape by the proposed macro-scale model. Wrinkle shape is more similar to that of meso-scale model, even though the wrinkle shapes are not in agreement completely. We can understand bending stiffness plays a very important role in the shape of wrinkles.

Fig.12. Comparison of wrinkling at punch stroke 20mm.

Fig.13. Comparison of wrinkling at punch stroke 30mm.

5 Conclusions

Two different approaches related to the scale for forming simulation of dry textile reinforcement are presented in this paper.

We can obtain each properties of dry fabric by meso-scale simulation. Then the macro-scale model that combines the membrane element and shell element is proposed. This macro-scale model can describe in-plane anisotropic behavior and out-plane bending stiffness that are obtained in meso-scale simulation. Finally we conduct the hemispherical preforming simulation and verify the macro-scale model by comparing it to the meso-scale model. Changing behavior of the fiber direction in the macro-scale model is very similar to that of the meso-scale model. The results of sensitivity study show that the shape of wrinkling can be influenced significantly by bending stiffness.

The proposed macro-scale model is proven to be able to evaluate the change in fiber direction and the shape of wrinkling.

Finally, the possibility of the meso-scale model is mentioned. The meo-scale model is a very attractive and time consuming approach. We can see that buckling at mesoscopic yarn level can be explicitly simulated in preforming simulation. Of course, this phenomenon at yarn level cannot be caught by the macro-scale model. We can observe only macroscopic wrinkling of the sheet buckling. Moreover, we can see the slip between warp and weft yarns in the meso-scale model where the friction coefficient is changed from 0.3 to 0.1. If this phenomenon occurs in the preforming process, this leads to the deterioration of strength and stiffness locally in the final product, because the volume fraction of carbon fiber decreases locally.

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